

INNOVATIVE APPROACH TO STUDENT EDUCATION ON THE BASE OF PIERLS'
TASKS

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Abstract: In this article, a new approach to the education of the young generation, which is a global problem in the age of information technologies, is discussed, the importance of PIRLS in this process and the methodology of its use are discussed

Key words: Innovation, PIRLS international assessment program, research, assignments, pedagogue, learner, society, outlook, thinking, etc.

Socio-economic changes in the society, sudden reforms entering the life of mankind require growth in all aspects. The main foundation of society's development is the young generation, perfect, well-rounded people with a broad worldview who contribute to the development of society based on universal values. In the rapidly changing times, education does not stand still! Various wonderful and interesting changes are taking place in a matter of seconds.

Including the development of the field of education cannot reach maturity without education. If we interpret this process on the basis of elementary school, the future of the great country is in the hands of the youth, and the main issue is to educate a perfect person in a country where freedom is protected. It is necessary to bring up generations who are interested, serve the people, respect the country, parents, and teachers, and love them immensely, in an innovative and creative spirit. Education is an intense process that continues continuously. Currently, the main basis of the achievements in the field of education has emerged by avoiding uniformity and falling into a permanent mold [1].

The PIRLS international study provides an international comparison of information on the level of development of reading comprehension skills of primary school students, which can serve public policy in the field of education to improve reading and teaching. provides analysis. This assessment program, which serves to develop many opportunities, was also considered important in the educational system of Uzbekistan and its practical application was introduced. Accordingly, according to the current PIRLS definition, reading literacy is the ability to understand and use the forms of written language required by society and valued by humans, as well as the ability to create meaning from texts in various forms. The reader is an active participant in this process, creating meaning, reflecting on the text, and consciously choosing effective reading strategies. Each type of text follows typical patterns and rules to help the reader interpret the text.

In the new way of education, it is necessary to awaken a great sense of responsibility in the consciousness of elementary school students and the young generation, and to develop their worldview under the influence of national values, universal traditions, and oriental spirit. In the process of educating primary school students, it is necessary to correctly approach the differences between the old views and newly emerging views in the psyche of children.

As social life, living conditions, and interpersonal relationships gain a new meaning, the content and methods of education and the attitude towards it also change. This process requires great responsibility from the teacher, because changes in society affect the personal qualities of

both the teacher and the student. Innovative ideas are primarily focused on the development of education.

PIRLS assesses elementary school students' classroom and extracurricular learning by focusing on two overarching goals: "acquiring artistic experiences" and "acquiring and using information." In turn, each of these goals integrates four broad comprehension processes.

But education cannot be brought to maturity without the development of education. That's why now only well-educated students, i.e. students who focus their attention, see their own interests, and control their ego, are brought into the innovative education system in a creative spirit. After all, the following thoughts of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, are noteworthy: It is the most important issue for us to develop young people who are capable of mobilizing, and every good thing has a bad side The reason is that there is an evil that strikes at the root of the ideas of goodness, the memory of the young generation has the idea of moving forward like an arrow, seeing both white and black as the same. [2].

In the study, how well do elementary school graduates of Uzbekistan study compared to their peers in other countries? What is the reading literacy of Uzbekistan's students? Is reading a hobby for 4th graders? How does the family contribute to the development of literacy? How is the process of teaching reading organized in our country today? Is the process of teaching reading in Uzbekistan unique compared to other countries, and if so, how does it manifest itself? Are the methods used by our primary school teachers different from the methods used by teachers in other countries? such basic issues are studied.

The main concern of today's pedagogues and parents is that children will absorb the "Wonderful" ideas coming from Western countries and European nations that are not compatible with Uzbek mentality, personality, and upbringing. It is impossible to keep children away from the social environment in order to protect them from the negative aspects of innovative ideas. After all, it is good to have a "golden mean" in everything. Ideas of creativity are opposed to restricting young people, because the developed education system develops human memory, enriches thinking in all aspects, and most importantly, develops students' speech, practical application of acquired knowledge, and practical skills in them. and promotes the use of methods aimed at creating skills.

An innovative educational pedagogue should create educational methodological complexes that are perfect in every way, use different methods during the lesson, not to bore the students, so that during the lesson they feel as if they were walking from garden to garden, can achieve the intended goal only due to fair criteria.

Participation in PIRLS allows Uzbekistan to independently objectively assess the level of reading skills among elementary school students. In addition, the openness and integration of Uzbekistan's education ensures the integration of the world's leading educational systems into the international community.

It is possible to develop a student's worldview by socializing him. Psychologically, there are different forms of memory, using which ideas of creativity can be instilled in students. Free and active thinking, modeling of the educational process, development of new ideas and technologies of education and training and its implementation will give high results. When the pedagogue has a pure heart, an open mind, and intelligence and intelligence, he can understand the feelings of young children being educated and approach them correctly [3].

A pedagogue who contributes to the development of the nation should adapt children to innovative ideas based on national values. Every person who considers himself a pedagogue should provide proper education and training to the children who have a strong heart, a beautiful face, and are seeking their teacher with their whole body. Creative pedagogues should educate children in such a way that bullets flash from their steps, the national anthem sounds behind them, the national flag flutters on their shoulders, the people rejoice, their parents are happy, and their teachers are proud.

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